

Does Lesson Study Influence Teachers' Perceptions, Understandings and Actions Relating to Inclusive Practice With Regards to Special Educational Needs in Mainstream Primary Mathematics?

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The pedagogical practices in mainstream settings for inclusion and the response to the identified and targeted needs for Special Educational Needs (SEN) learners appear somewhat fragile and indeed fragmented. There is a gap between the knowledge and theory of SEN and actual practice, and this is evident in primary mathematics. Teacher Professional Development (PD) plays a pivotal role in supporting schools towards the inclusion of SEN learners. It is prudent that the PD needs of teachers address this gap. This case study follows two primary schools as they develop a Professional Learning Community (PLC) and engage in the Lesson Study (LS) process to support their PD regarding the inclusion of SEN learners in mainstream primary mathematics. Underpinned by the Teaching for Robust Understanding (TRU) framework in mathematics (Schoenfeld, 2018) and focused on case study pupils (Dudley, 2013), the LS cycle is framed by the teacher participants experiencing mathematics through the eyes of the child, and in this case, the SEN learner. Early findings show that teachers developed PCK for mathematics teaching. They also collaborated effectively to understand and direct the mathematical trajectories for their SEN learners and made connections to all their learners. In this case, LS shows promise and potential as a sustainable form of teacher PD that can support the inclusion of all learners in an inclusive mainstream setting.

Introduction

Unlike in Japan, LS is not as widespread a practice in Ireland, where it is an emerging form of PD for teachers at the primary level. It is suggested that the LS approach is integral to schooling in Japan, and efforts to understand it better outside of this context require a focus on the features and the theories that underpin it. This leads to a situation in Ireland that requires greater attention to teacher PD forms and how schools can adapt approaches such as LS to meet their context and situation. According to Gero (2014), LS is much more than a set of procedures driven by fundamental themes that reflect the Japanese culture. The critical features of LS can be linked to Japan's culture of interdependence, an emphasis on continuous effort, and the practice of critical reflection (Heine et al., 1999; Stevenson & Stigler, 1992). The methods associated with LS are consistent with the implicit values and beliefs shared by the general society in Japan, and that reflects their culture and historical experience. LS echoes the collaborative approach and emphasises the interdependence between its citizens and its esteemed Japanese culture. The admirable mindset and diligence that crafts teaching practice indicate and characterise the emphasis that Japanese people tend to place on hard work (Seleznyov, 2018). Finally, the expectation that teachers think critically about their practice evokes the self-critical mindset prevalent in Japanese individuals (OECD, 2010). These signature qualities that underpin LS may prove problematic when applied in a western culture that reveres individualism, celebrates personal ability, and shelters self-esteem (Kitayama et al., 1997; Whang & Hancock, 1994). Thus, the sustainability of any adaption of

LS into western contexts such as Ireland needs to be mindful of the cultural differences within which they work. It is fundamental to understand and consider how to respond to meet teachers' PD needs in response to their context, the pupils they teach and the identified gaps and needs within each setting. As Huang, Takahashi, and Ponte (2019) assert, numerous challenges and barriers face the adoption of LS, but emphasise that the theories supporting Lesson Study and the research methods for Lesson Study are now emerging as research issues.

The purpose of LS as it is practised in Japan is much broader than is often appreciated in western cultures (Lewis et al., 2019); Huang et al. (2019). In the Japanese context, the LS process is intended to not just lead to improved teaching but to support a more profound sense of professional community among teachers (Lewis, Perry and Hurd, 2009; Sato 2008), to facilitate teacher understanding of curriculum reforms and of the national performance indicators (Takahashi & McDougal 2014). LS also assists teachers to bring about in their daily teaching, the shared long term vision for their pupils devised collaboratively by the school (Takahashi & McDougal 2016). Given this context, adapting LS to meet the PD needs of primary teachers who aim to create inclusive learning experiences in the context of mainstream mathematics for their learners seems novel and intriguing.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive education is founded on the principle that each child, irrespective of their gender, social class, cultural background or ability level, has the right to an education in a mainstream setting (Westwood, 2007). Despite this principle informing educational policy formation in many western countries, the actual practice of the inclusion of SEN learners is not always consistent with policy. It depends on teacher perceptions and understandings of inclusion and attitudes towards SEN learners presenting in the mainstream setting (Brennan et al., 2019). Perceptions, attitudes, and understanding of SEN pupils and their needs significantly impact the success or otherwise of the inclusion process in educational contexts and, particularly, a willingness among school personnel to contribute to the inclusion process (Skidmore, 2004). An SEN learner's learning difficulties can generally influence a teacher's perceptions, beliefs, and subsequent actions regarding the inclusion process and SEN learners.

Schools respond to greater diversity today (Ainscow, 2020; Brennan et al. 2019). How schools respond to inclusion is related to teachers' attitudes, knowledge, skills, capacity and understanding (Hornby, 2010; Horne & Timmons, 2009). While Rose et al. (2015) report many teachers do not possess the knowledge, skills and understanding to craft the necessary inclusive learning environment, how teachers' access professional development to equip themselves with the required skills to embrace inclusion in their unique school context appears unclear. This research investigates if the LS model of sustained teacher professional development and learning can support teachers' understandings, perceptions and actions to co-construct the necessary inclusive primary mathematics classroom. This study seeks to track and record if a sustained model of inquiry-based teacher professional development such as

Lesson Study leads mainstream teachers and Special Education Teachers (SET) to improve their mathematical PCK collaboratively. The study aims to facilitate teacher learning as they respond to the inclusion of SEN learners in the primary mathematics classroom. The research phase supports the team to plan a lesson that promotes their inquiry. This study seeks to support a system that facilitates mainstream teachers and SETs to collaborate to meet SEN pupils' identified and targeted needs in the mainstream primary mathematics classroom.

The Context of this Study

The Inclusive Pedagogical Approach informed the Lesson Study community in Action (IPAA) framework (Florian, 2014), the Teaching for Robust Understanding framework (TRU) (Schoenfeld, 2013), the case study pupil approach (Dudley, 2013), adapted for SEN learners informed the research and planning phase of the LS cycle. The development of teacher PCK was captured using a thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) approach to generating qualitative data generated during the study.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge

Developed by Schulman (1986), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) is identified by Ball, Thames & Phelps (2008) as Knowledge of Content and Students (KCS), such as the "knowledge that combines knowing about students and knowing about mathematics" (p. 401). In LS, both PCK on action (the knowledge, skills, reasons and planning, and beliefs) as well as PCK in action (teaching specific content in class) are addressed as in the action research paradigm of Schön (1983). PCK is constructed in a complex manner in which teachers actively make sense of the knowledge base, subject-specific knowledge, teacher and pupils' beliefs, and learning outcomes. An expert teacher has well-formed PCK for all topics taught, developed, and shaped in regular classroom practice and supported through reflection. Early career teachers need to build and expand their PCK (Ni Shúilleabháin, 2016) and models of teacher inquiry that promote collaboration, building trust and sharing of expertise facilitate this process. This is the case with all teachers when collaboratively planning to meet the individual academic needs of an SEN learner in the mainstream setting (Florian, 2014; Friend et al., 2010).

Teaching for Robust Understanding (TRU)

The five dimensions of the TRU framework describe the necessary attributes that illustrate methods of teaching which can support learners to be knowledgeable, flexible, and resourceful thinkers and problem solvers. By engaging in the TRU framework, there is a change in focus from a teacher-centred to a student-centred perspective. Teacher learning and reflections ask not: "Do I like what the teacher is doing?" instead "What does instruction feel like, from the point of view of the student?" This emphasises how the learners have meaningful opportunities to make sense of the mathematical content. This perspective is represented in Figure 1 below. The TRU framework does not say how to teach, as it recognises the variety that constitutes effective teaching. TRU serves to problematise instruction to support rich teaching that does not impose a prescribed approach on teachers.

The TRU offers an outlook for teaching and the necessary language for dialogue regarding pedagogy in mathematics in a convincing manner.

Figure 1

Observing a mathematics lesson from the student perspective (Schoenfeld, 2018).

Observe the lesson through a student's eyes	
The Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What's the big idea in this lesson? How does it connect to what I already know?
Cognitive Demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How long am I given to think, and to make sense of things? What happens when I get stuck? Am I invited to explain things, or just give answers?
Equitable Access to Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do I get to participate in meaningful mathematical learning? Can I hide or be ignored?
Agency, Ownership, and Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do I get to explain, to present my ideas? Are they built on? Am I recognized as being capable and able to contribute in meaningful ways?
Formative Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do classroom discussions include my thinking? Does instruction respond to my thinking and help me think more deeply?

Case Study & Reflective Practice

A qualitative inquiry informs the data generated for this case study. The researcher sought to create a rich dialogic space to research the teacher learning among the participating teachers. This rich talk took place in two primary school settings as teachers engaged in the LS process to sustain teacher professional development and learning, which yielded qualitative data for analysis. Throughout the LS process, the research investigates teacher learning in a social space in which teachers negotiated and made sense of their learning. This study aims to capture and illuminate the learning that took place in the dialogic space (supported by the research phase and the lesson planning phase of the Lesson Study cycle), that could be described as surprising, challenging, reflective and marks changes in the perceptions and understandings of knowledge in the teaching of SEN learners in the mainstream primary mathematics setting. In this case, these experiences supported and nurtured the trust to build among the teacher participants to allow for the uniqueness of the situation to emerge. The teachers shared ideas, observations, reflections, experiences and their new learning. The case study approach included reflective practice for both the teacher participants and the researcher. Having access to this dialogic space supported teachers to critically reflect on their perceptions and understandings of the inclusion of SEN learners in their school setting. It made it clear the knowledge they acquired by engaging in the Lesson Study process.

Early Data Analysis, Tentative Findings and Discussion

LS was a novel form of teacher PD that challenged traditional approaches to mainstream mathematics classrooms. It offered participants space and time to inquire, research, experiment, reflect and collaboratively learn as a community of learners. It was a safe space to engage with new approaches to teaching mathematics and learn from one another and build on this knowledge. A key theme that is tentatively emerging at this early stage of data analysis regards supporting all the learners in the mainstream setting, not just the SEN learner.

Concluding Thoughts and Reflections

In this study, teacher participants used the research phase of LS to engage with the IPAA framework (Florian, 2014), the TRU framework (Schoenfeld, 2013), and the case study pupil approach (Dudley, 2013) adapted for SEN learners. The development of teacher PCK was captured using a thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2006) based upon the qualitative data generated during the study. The LS cycle shows promise as the PD takes place within the school setting. It involves collaboration, requires the teachers to engage with research, reflection and inquiry while enabling them to plan with the needs of the SEN learner in mind.

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